

Ålands Hushållningssällskap rf.

12.9.2025

Letter of Support for Blue Islands Living Labs (BLISS) - Åland

To the European Commission,

Ålands Hushållningssällskap is pleased to provide this letter of support for the BLISS proposal under Horizon Europe.

Ålands Hushållningssällskap is a non-profit and the official advising organisation for agriculture on Åland Islands. We are partly funded by the Government of Åland and in charge of advising, development issues and projects related to agriculture as well as running a trial orchard for fruit farming.

We recently participated in the project Kolsänkor på Åland (lead organisation were Åland University of Applied Sciences), where one of the results were regarding the use of biochar for increased carbon storage in soil. This would also improve soil health, reduce nutrient losses in soil and improve soil structure. Another development project we are currently participating in is GYPREG (Interreg Central Baltic), where Åland is a test site and partner for gypsum treatment also used for improving soil health. Both methods (gypsum and biochar) are currently highly interesting techniques for agriculture on Åland, and we look forward to participating in the BLISS project as well.

We particularly value the participation of Åland University of Applied Sciences and the Government of Åland, alongside the Mariehamn municipality.

This project represents an excellent opportunity to:

- *Address the key challenges of the Baltic Sea Region and the strong local development of agricultural practices related to these issues*
- *Strengthen collaboration between European University Alliances focused on maritime innovation*
- *Demonstrate practical applications of research in sustainable ocean management*
- *Create synergies between academic excellence and industry innovation, through mutual benefits and economic profitability throughout the value chain*
- *Support the development of next-generation maritime professionals*

We endorse this proposal and look forward to exploring future collaboration opportunities with the BLISS consortium.

Sincerely,

Jenny Enbär
CEO, Ålands Hushållningssällskap rf.